

SOP Verification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* magnetic capture method in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces and proficiency test.

1. Aim of method

This method describes the verification panel for ensuring that the homogenisation and capture of *Echinococcus* DNA from red fox faecal samples using a magnetic capture method combined with PCR (Isaksson et al. 2014; Øines et al. 2014) has performed satisfactorily.

2. References

- 2.1. Isaksson M, Hagström Å, Armua-Fernandez MT, Wahlström H, Ågren EO, Miller A, Holmberg A, Lukacs M, Casulli A, Deplazes P, Juremalm M. A semi-automated magnetic capture probe-based DNA extraction and real-time PCR method applied in the Swedish surveillance of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples. *Parasit Vectors*. 2014 Dec 19;7:583.
<https://parasitesandvectors.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13071-014-0583-6>
- 2.2. Øines Ø, Isaksson M, Hagström Å, Tavoranpanich S, Davidson RK., Laboratory assessment of sensitive molecular tools for detection of low levels of *Echinococcus multilocularis* eggs in fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces. *Parasit Vectors*. 2014; 7(1):246.
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/1756-3305-7-246>

3. Method summary and Test Performance

This method describes the design of the verification panel, information about the proficiency test panel, and the reporting of the results. Please note that DNA extraction is based upon the extraction of mitochondrial DNA and therefore any subsequent PCR methods should detect mitochondrial DNA.

The verification panel is for the in-house testing of the DNA extraction and PCR methods to identify any problems prior to the screening of samples and proficiency test panels.

4. Principles

The principles behind the magnetic capture method involve red fox faecal samples, potentially containing the target mitochondrial DNA, homogenized in a buffer with zirconium oxide beads to disrupt cestode eggs and segments of cestodes to release target DNA in solution. The resultant debris is centrifuged and the supernatant extracted for use in the rest of the protocol. The samples are cleaned of natural biotin content by using streptavidin sepharose, thus preventing later interference with the biotin-streptavidin binding during extraction. A biotin-labelled DNA-capture probe is then added to the sample.

Denaturation at 98°C separates the target DNA-strands and allows hybridization of the capture probe at a specific binding site on the mitochondrial DNA during the cooling step to 55°C. Streptavidin coated paramagnetic beads are then added to the sample. The target DNA/capture probe complex binds to the magnetic beads through the biotin-streptavidin binding. The DNA/capture probe/magnetic bead complex is washed a number of times by using a magnet to pellet the beads and changing the washing buffer. To remove the target DNA from the bead the complex is heated to 99°C and the beads are collected again using a magnet. The supernatant containing the target DNA, without beads, is transferred to a new tube/plate and can be used in further molecular analysis. The choice of PCR detection method is up to each participating laboratory although we recommend using at least one or both of Isaksson et al. 2014 and/or Øines et al. 2014.

5. Warnings/HMS measures

EM is a zoonotic parasite and therefore the laboratory needs to follow their HMS guidelines with regard to limiting exposure to this parasite. Infection occurs via the oral transmission of EM eggs and can result tumour like growths in a number of internal organs, including the liver and brain.

Minimum HMS requirements are that all samples are frozen prior to handling to inactivate any potential oocysts (-80°C at the core of the sample for a minimum of 48 hours) and that gloves are used at all times even after freezing.

The lab should be divided into different work zones for the different stages of sample preparation and DNA extraction. The in-house chemicals are prepared in a separate laboratory to where DNA extraction will be carried out. The sample handling and DNA extraction is carried out in a designated zoonosis lab which has restricted access. We chose to work with samples that are frozen to -80°C for a minimum of 56 hours. We use gloves throughout the process and during the weighing of faeces we work in a fume cupboard to minimize the potential contamination of other work surfaces in the zoonosis lab. The division of zones and laboratories will depend on the facilities you have available.

6. Chemicals and Reagents

See the individual SOPs for the full list of chemical reagents for the magnetic capture and PCR methods.

The verification panel consists of 32 tubes containing samples spiked with 1 egg, 5 eggs, 10 eggs, whole worm with and without fox faeces. These samples should then be processed according to the SOP. The red fox faeces is based on a homogenised sample obtained from wild red foxes from Norway that have previously been analysed for *Echinococcus multilocularis* and found to be negative.

Table 1 List of chemicals and reagents used to carry out the *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA magnetic capture method

Description	Contents	Provided by	Article no.	Used at step:
Red fox faeces	Homogenised faeces from the Norwegian national surveillance program for <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> , Each laboratory will be provided with two 50 g samples of this homogenised faeces for spiking purposes.	NVI		
Echinococcus eggs and whole worms	2 cryotubes containing 10 EM worms in each	NVI		
Proficiency panel	Panel of at least ten 15mL tubes containing zirconium beads, 3 g fox faeces and spiked with varying amounts of Em eggs/worms.	NVI		
Special TE buffer	See Magnetic capture SOP for information on buffers			
5M NaCl	See Magnetic capture SOP for information on buffers			
Ethanol				
Zirconium beads	See Magnetic capture SOP for information on beads			

7. Controls

Each participating laboratory should prepare their own EBC (E blank control).

8. Equipment and instruments

Again refer to the SOP for magnetic capture for the list of equipment required to complete the method.

Table 2 List of equipment that is needed to carry out the *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA magnetic capture method

Item	Description	Producer	Article number	Used at step ^b :
15 mL plastic tubes ^{a*}	Sarstedts screwtop or those supplied with FastPrep	Sarsted	#62.554.502	
Weighing scales	Sensitive to ± 0.1 g			
Stereomicroscope	With direct lighting from below and, if possible, oblique/diagonal lighting			
Automatic pipette	For volumes 1-10 μ L			
Pipette tips	1-10 μ L			
Petri-dish				
Glass slides (microscope)				

^aThe robustness of the tubes is a critical step during homogenisation. We recommend using the tubes identified here since these have proven their robustness whilst other brands have cracked/leaked during the homogenisation step.

9. Workflow and full method description

Verification is based upon the analysis of 24 tubes containing 3 g fox faeces with a known number of *Echinococcus* eggs as well as 8 tubes containing only parasites and no faecal matrix.

The proficiency test is based on the analysis of 10 faecal samples with unknown parasite status.

Table 3 Showing the PCR plate set up for verification as well as how many eggs/worms in each sample

EBC ¹	Fox 1 - 1 egg A	Fox 2 - 1 egg A	Fox 3 - 1 egg A	No faeces - 1 egg A
	Fox 1 - 1 egg B	Fox 2 - 1 egg B	Fox 3 - 1 egg B	No faeces 1 egg B
	Fox 1 - 5 eggs A	Fox 2 - 5 eggs A	Fox 3 - 5 eggs A	No faeces 5 eggs A
	Fox 1 - 5 eggs B	Fox 2 - 5 eggs B	Fox 3 - 5 eggs B	No faeces 5 eggs B
	Fox 1 - 10 eggs A	Fox 2 - 10 eggs A	Fox 3 - 10 eggs A	No faeces 10 eggs A
	Fox 1 - 10 eggs B	Fox 2 - 10 eggs B	Fox 3 - 10 eggs B	No faeces 10 eggs B
	Fox 1 – whole worm A	Fox 2 – whole worm A	Fox 3 – whole worm A	No faeces whole worm A
	Fox 1 – whole worm B	Fox 2 – whole worm B	Fox 3 – whole worm B	No faeces whole worm B

¹ EBC is the extraction blank control

9.1. Verification Sample preparation

Location: Prep lab or separate area

9.1.1. Label 33 x 15mL homogenization tubes and preload with the zirconium beads as per the magnetic capture DNA extraction method.

- 9.1.2. Place the faecal samples on the bench at room temperature until defrosted, if needed, otherwise proceed directly to next step. The faecal samples are labelled fox 1, fox 2, fox 3.
- 9.1.3. Weigh 3 g (\pm 0.1) fox faeces into each tube and fill 8 tubes per faecal sample. You should end up with 8 tubes containing faeces from fox 1, 8 tubes from fox 2 and 8 tubes from fox 3. Each fox has 2 tubes with 1 egg, 2 tubes with 5 eggs, 2 tubes with 10 eggs and two tubes with whole worms.
- 9.1.4. The remaining 9 tubes DO NOT have faeces in them.
- 9.1.5. Centrifuge the tubes containing the beads and the faeces as per the magnetic capture DNA extraction method.
- 9.1.6. Add 9mL special TE and 3mL 5M NaCl (as per the magnetic capture DNA extraction method)
- 9.1.7. To transfer the requisite number of eggs or worm to each tube (see Table 3 for the set up). Transfer the eggs/worms to a petridish with ethanol (same strength as that which the worms are sent in).
- 9.1.8. Place the petri-dish under a stereomicroscope. If necessary, break a gravid segment to release the eggs.
- 9.1.9. One a microscope glass, placed next to the petri-dish on the microscope) place a drop of ethanol.
- 9.1.10. Now transfer the require number of eggs from the petri-dish to the microscope glass using a pipette with a 1-10 μ L tip.
- 9.1.11. Check that the number of eggs is correct before transferring them, again using a pipette, to the correct tube.
- 9.1.12. Double check that there are no eggs remaining on the microscope slide or in the pipette tip by examining both under the stereomicroscope.
- 9.1.13. The samples are now ready to carry out the magnetic capture and molecular detection as described in the SOP.

9.2. The proficiency test samples

- 9.2.1. These should only be analysed once the verification panel has shown that the method is working satisfactorily at your laboratory.
- 9.2.2. Each tube contains 3 g of fox faeces with unknown contamination status. Each sample should be analysed using the method described in the relevant SOPs for magnetic capture and PCR analysis.

10. Interpretation and reporting of the results

10.1. Verification panel

When at least one of the duplicate samples (either A or B) are positive then that sample is recorded as *E. multilocularis* detected.

If the EBC and negative control samples test positive then verification is not approved.

If none of the samples with faeces test positive yet the majority of the samples without faeces that have eggs and worms test positive then there is a problem with faecal inhibition in the samples.

If only the samples with whole worms test positive then there is a problem with low sensitivity in the method.

It is not unusual for one or more of the samples with only 1 egg to test negative. As long as all the other samples have been correctly identified then the verification panel is approved.

10.2. Proficiency test panel

The results should be reported as *Echinococcus multilocularis* detected or not detected for each sample. Additional information about date the test received, date the test was analysed, which magnetic capture SOP used, which PCR was used, additional verification results of positive samples will need to be recorded on the result reporting form (Annex 1) and returned to the proficiency test provider within two weeks of completing the analysis and no later than 1 month after receiving the proficiency test.

11. Storage of the Samples

The samples can be stored at $\leq -15^{\circ}\text{C}$ until analysis can be carried out.

12. Disposal of waste materials

Follow your laboratory guidelines for the disposal of biohazardous waste.

12.1 Gloves and paper waste are autoclaved prior to disposal as normal waste.

12.2 The remains of the biological samples and equipment that has been in contact with the biological material is disposed of in a yellow biohazard container, which is sent for incineration once full.

Annex 1 Proficiency Test Reporting Form

Laboratory ID

Date received PT
at lab:

Investigator ID^a

Date analysis
reported:

Sample ID	Date analysed	DNA extraction method ¹	PCR method ²	Result ³

^a Name in block capitals and signature at bottom of the page

¹ Magnetic capture method: Manual washing SOP or Automatic washing SOP

² PCR methods: Isaksson et al. 2014, Øines et al. 2014, Trachsel et al. 2007, other (please indicate which one used).

³ Results reported as “detected” or “not detected”

Additional comments to PT

Signature of Investigator